

Marriage Postponement During Covid-19 Pandemic: A Study of Its Implementation in Manado City, North Sulawesi Province

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Abstract

This study aims to identify the implications on the post-issuance of the Director General of Islamic Community Guidance (Ditjen Bimas) Circular Letter regarding the postponement of marriage since the second of April up to a new circular issuance on the Covid-19 pandemic. This is a field research, and the technique conducted during the Work From Home (WFH) period was to apply technology and social networks to assist researchers in obtaining data. The research stages include observation, interview, and documentation. The results find that there are three negative implications; social, juridical, and fiqhiyyah aspects. In the social aspect, the postponement of marriage in the pandemic period inspired some residents to hold unregistered marriage. In the juridical aspect, various individual interpretations "ijtihad" were stated by heads of the Office of Religious Affairs (KUA) that exceeded their authority. Whereas in the fiqhiyyah aspect, the values of benefit which are used as arguments for justification of unregistered marriage are simplistic, because they do not use the ushul fiqh as a parameter.

Keywords: Implications; Circular Letter of Marriage Postponement; Covid-19 Pandemic Period

1. Introduction

Getting married is a sunnatullah which is urged by Allah SWT in the QS. an-Nisa' verse (3) by using the verb command (amar) fankihu (then marry by you), and the Prophet as the deliverer of His treatise emphasizes mentioning the practice of marriage as his sunnah.[1, p. 1949], [2, p. 1020], [3, p. 368] The implication is when someone is unable to master himself because not married yet which may cause the presence of disadvantages (mudharat) in the form of disobedience or adultery. Therefore, the scholars give legal status mubah in a normal condition. However if it is done to prevent adultery, the law of marriage rises to become mandatory on a person.[1, p. 1950]

However, since the corona 19 virus (hereinafter referred to as covid-19) spread into Indonesia, confirmed in the city of Manado in the early March, various activities in the community both in the office sector, education, etc., were temporarily stopped and replaced by Work From Home (WFH) program which mainly uses the internet as its working base. In fact, in order to prevent the wider spread of covid-19 in the society, various circulations and regulations from the central government were born which must be implemented throughout Indonesian territory. One of them is a Circular Letter from the Directorate General of Islamic Community Guidance Number: P-003 / DJ.III / Hk.00.7 / 04/2020 concerning the Amendments of the Directorate General of Islamic Community Guidance Circular Letter Number: P-002 / DJ.III / Hk. 00.7 / 03/2020 concerning the Implementation of Covid-19 Handling Protocol in Public Areas within the Directorate General of Islamic Community Guidance, dated 02 April 2020.

There are at least two important points to be criticized in this study, namely the E provisions number 3 point a number 2 and 7 which contents: (1) Number 2: Requests of new registration for the procession of a marriage contract in the Covid-19 emergency period are not served and the communities are urged to postpone their procession; (2) Number 7: Online marriage contract processions whether through telephone, video call, or use of other web-based applications are not permitted.

Based on the two dictum orders, all marriage registration activities held by the Office of Religious Affairs (hereinafter referred to as KUA) for marriages were postponed in April until the latest circular letter.

The refusal of KUA officers to register marriage since the beginning of April becomes a problem for Muslim community in Manado City. As consequence, the practice of unregistered marriage of the community arises with the justification to avoid sin and disadvantages by the prospectus bride and groom.[4] Based on these problems, this research was conducted to explore the implications of the circular letter with the locus of the research is the City of Manado.

2. Research Methods

This research is a field research that used a qualitative approach to explore the implications of the issuance of the Circular from the Director General of Islamic Community Guidance dated 02 April 2020 which postponed all marriages in the community due to the covid-19 pandemic in Manado City. Field data collection during the pandemic was taken by following the procedure of WFH which consists of three stages by utilizing digital technology and social networks to assist researchers in obtaining data, namely; observations of several marital events that held after the issuance of Islamic Community Guidance Circular Letter. The research stages were carried out by research assistants scattered in several areas of research objects include live interviews with Section Head of the Islamic Community Guidance at the Office of the Ministry of Religion in the City of Manado, involving several Heads of KUA in the City of Manado, and several perpetrators or families who continue to carry out marriages after the issuance of the circulation. The interviews were through telephone facilities that were recorded. The electronic documentation of marriages which taken place after the circular issuance dated two April was filed. The data analysis is carried out inductively with stages; data reduction, data presentation or display, and making conclusion or verification.

3. Field Data Findings

The city of Manado is the capital of North Sulawesi Province, located at the northern tip of the peninsula of Sulawesi. The geographical position is 124 ° 40 ' - 124 ° 50 ' East Longitude and 1 ° 30 ' - 1 ° 40 ' North Latitude with a land area of 15,726 hectares. Its occupation in terms of religious choices based on population census data in 2010 was 62.10 percent Christian, 5.02 percent Catholic, while Muslims 31.30 percent and the rest were other religions. The populations were spread in eleven districts, namely Wanea, Wenang, Tuminting, Tikala, Singkil, Sario, Paal Dua, Mapanget, Malalayang, Bunaken Kepulauan, Bunaken.[5]

Based on the region profile, it was unfortunate that the number of KUA in Manado City is only ten offices located in Wanea, Wenang, Tuminting, Tikala, Singkil, Sario, Paal Dua, Mapanget, Malalayang, and Bunaken Districts, while the services for Bunaken Kepulauan residents are directed to KUA of Bunaken District. Although Muslim population is a minority in Manado City, religious services such as marriage registration requests throughout the KUA have been going well.

However since the covid-19 pandemic took place in Manado City, there have been various obstacles in providing services, especially after the WFH ordered by the government. It continues and the peak was after the Director General of Islamic Community Guidance of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia issued a circular letter ordering all KUAs to postpone all marriage registration activities from the second of April to the twenty-first of April or after a new circular letter order the re-opening of registration and recording services for marriage by the KUA.

After the order to suspend the registration of marriages, various actions and reactions were done by several KUA heads in response to the circular. The obtained data from at least seven KUA heads who can be confirmed and interviewed revealed that not all KUA heads read in detail the contents of the circular which leading to various actions that different among KUA.

The interview that were held produced at least three core data to point, they are: the acceptance of marriage registration after the circular issuance, the procession of the marriage contract and the recording of marriage after the date of the promulgation, the KUAs action on the application on marriage registration after the implementation of the marriage postponement circular for those who were in very urgent situations such as unwed pregnancy and the acceleration of the marriage ceremony due to urgent official obligations from registrant's working place in the form of either placement of assignments or mutations to remote areas.

Regarding the first data, the acceptance of marriage registration by KUA was still conducted as indicated by the seven interviewed KUA. There were only three out of seven KUAs which did not receive marriage registration since the enactment of the circular of the Director General of Islamic Community Guidance, namely KUA of Singkil, Tuminting, and Wenang Districts. While the other four KUAs still received marriage registration, but it was conducted manually because the online marriage registration system through the SIMKAH application has been closed since the circulation took effect. However, from the four KUAs that received manual registration, there were two KUAs namely Tikala and Mapanget which proceed the marriage registration agenda for an urgent event. The other two KUA namely Paal Dua and Malalayang obliged the bride and the groom to obey the circular by carrying out the marriage contract after the twenty first of April or after a new circulation issuance.[6]

The second data is about marriage implementation and marriage registration after the promulgation of the marriage postponement. Out of of the seven KUAs, there was only one KUA which no longer conducted the marriage registration service, namely KUA of Tuminting District. The KUA called on the citizens to postpone the marriage contract until there is a new circular of marriage contract. The other six KUAs still implemented it but with certain conditions. This decisive decision was made due to security reasons and preventing the spread of the corona virus which was the main reason for the issuance of the circular, so that the KUAs as a lower-level state apparatus was obliged to obey the commands of the circular.[7]

Data from KUA of Tikala District, there were several marriages which agenda were recorded before April and five other marriages after the issuance of the circular letter due to a very urgent matters such as unwed pregnancy and job needs because their prospectus partners will be sent for work service immediately in a remote area for a long time. Those conditional marriage contracts were proceed by practicing the implementation of health and safety protocols during the covid-19 pandemic like physical distancing obligations and only maximum of ten attendees.[8]

Mapanget sub-district KUA is very flexible and open by continuing to receive registration and hold marriage contract procession and marriage registration even though there is a circular which requires a postponement of the marriage from the second to the twenty first of April. It is because the marriage contract is the community need that cannot be detained, so that presenting benefit must be prioritized rather than disadvantages. According to the official, there are ten marriages were conducted due to family insistence, with the condition that the Head of KUA explained in advance that there was a circular regarding marriage delays before accepting marriage registration and procession. They can make compromise with the parties like family, and if the family still wants the wedding schedule according to the planned time, the marriage contract and the registration were held with the obligation of no more than ten attendees. Apart from that, there were also five pairs of bride and groom who had registered their wedding plans in the middle of April, but until the interview was held it was not yet confirmed when the planned marriage contract would be held.[9]

At the KUA of Singkil District, there were seven contract and marriage registration activities because the registration had been done before the circular issuance, but after the circular announced, all activities were postponed until a new circular letter. According to the interview, this decision was taken because the task of the KUA at this time was to obey the circular, and so that the public can know it. The KUA was obliged to socialize it both verbally and non-verbally, such as by posting it on the bulletin board and by giving an explanation when someone came to register his marriage plans.[10]

The KUA of Wenang Subdistrict held four marriages that took place after the circular issuance, which marriage registration at the KUA had been submitted before the circular issuance.[11] KUA of Malalayang District also applies the same thing, there are two marriage events that had been recorded by KUA after the issuance of the circular, but the registration had been done before the circular issuance.[12] Likewise with KUA of Paal Dua, where there is one wedding event conducted after the circulation issuance but the registration had been carried out since March.[13] . The arguments built by the three KUA above are normative, as servants of the state they are obliged to carry out the tasks that have been directed through the circular letter.

The findings regarding the KUA's attitude towards very urgent marriage requests after the implementation of postponement of marriage are quite diverse. KUA of Singkil and Tuminting Subdistricts firmly refused to serve such request, because the circular clearly prohibited the activity for the sake of all people health by avoiding covid-19 spread.[7], [10] The KUA of Paal Dua District demonstrated the attitude to continue receiving marriage registration, but the procession is managed after the twenty-first of April or after a new circular revokes the previous circular.[13]

KUA of Malalayang District is not going to serve such request, but if it is very urgent it will be directed to marry in the method of Islamic Shari'ah only through local mosque priests and not in the KUA. Subsequently, after a new circular issued the married couple must make a request of itsbat marriage to the Religious Court.[12] The same thing is also done by KAU of Wenang Sub-district, but the difference is that the marriage must still be known by the KUA so that when the circular has been revoked the unregistered marriage in the case can be renewed through the marriage ceremony to get a marriage book.[11]

Whereas the last two KUAs, namely KUA of Tikala and Mapanget sub-districts, still administratively carried their services out and published marriage books. The difference is, for KUA Tikala District only accepts very urgent requests, such as

unwed pregnancy or because of the obligation of office duties, for those who are not so urgent will be postponed until a new circular issuance.[8] While KUA Mapanget clearly provides information to accept and carry out marriages either urgently or not based on the will of the family who will make the event, because delaying a marriage is an attitude that will result more disadvantages.[9]

After conducting interviews with the heads of the KUA and obtaining the above data, a confirmation was made to the Section Head of the Islamic Community Guidance of the Ministry of Religion in the City of Manado. The data shows that all the heads of the KUA had received guidance on the implementation of the circular letter and all were required to implement it, aside from there are accidental cases such as getting unwed pregnancy and requesting marriage to maintain the good name of the family and religion, marriage is permitted but with manual registration. However, until this interview is released, according to Sahrir, there is no information from the KUA heads whether there is a marriage procession conducted due to such accident.[14] This final explanation shows that there is no systematic monitoring and evaluation of the implementation of the circular letter in all KUA in the city of Manado, otherwise there was only an ordinary communication, both from Bimas to KUA or vice versa.[14]

After digging up data from the implementers of the rules, the next step is to scrutinize the information from the community, either those directly affected by the circular implementation or the priests who have been the forefront of assisting KUA in the procession of the marriage contract in the community. The results of observations found the practices of unregistered marriage in the districts which explicitly implements marriage postponement fully.

In the Tuminting Sub district, there were three practices of unregistered marriage after the postponement of the marriage ceremony, which was carried out directly by the trustees, but the ceremony was not publicized, worrying about negative impacts in the future, especially when the bride and the groom wanted to ratify their marriage in order to obtain a marriage book at KUA. The main reason why the marriage must be carried out is because the parents feel that if the closeness of their son with his girlfriend will lead to sinful acts, the marriage should be carried out immediately. On the other hand, another procession is conducted for a very urgent reason.[15]

In the Singkil Sub district, there were two unregistered marriage contract procession. One of them cannot be confirmed because of refusal to be interviewed, while the other couple could be confirmed. The confirming couple said that the marriage contract was guided by one of the religious leaders at the place of the marriage, with very simple preparation, presented by only the bride and groom, the direct marriage trustee of the bride's parents, two witnesses, and several family members, no more than fifteen people attending the party. The ceremony was not documented or posted on their social media. After being confirmed, it was found that the reason for the procession of marriage contract because of a very urgent matter that was not clarified in detail by the interviewees, but essentially, the marriage must be carried out as soon as possible. Thus, when they find out that there were rules in the KUA which postponed requests of any marriage contract and activities. Additionally, the parents of the bride and the groom insisted for the marriage to be carried out in Islamic sharia in advance.[16, p. Singkil]

In the Malalayang Subdistrict, at least there was one marriage event recorded from a couple who came from outside of the area but were domiciled in one of the Malalayang Sub district areas because of employment condition. This information was obtained from informants who did not want to be exposed for reasons of

closeness as a close colleague as well as a neighbor in the neighboring. When investigating the reason why his close friend married during the corona pandemic with unregistered marital status, the main reason was because of the "accident" due to promiscuity, and the woman's parents urged the marriage to be carried out though not registered in the KUA, the marriage book will only be done if the covid-19 emergency period has ended.[17]

4. The Implications of Marriage Postponement by the State

Based on the field data that has been presented, it was found that there were negative implications after the birth of a circular from the Director General of the Islamic Guidance Center, so that the KUA postponed the wedding plans of their respective citizens. The implication is the rise of unregistered marriage that may harm the legal order in Indonesia.

The history shows that after the regulation on marriage in Indonesia was promulgated in 1974, there has never been a new regulation after its issuance. Even there was none of a circular letter which postponed the marriage due to certain reasons. It is the first, in April 2020, due to the outbreak of covid-19 in the midst of Indonesian society in various regions including the city of Manado, the situation forced the government, in this case the Religion Ministry of Indonesia - to issue a circular letter ordering all KUA to postpone marriage registration activities from the beginning of April until a new revoked circular issued, with the reason to prevent the spread of Covid-19 in the country.

Normatively, the government's expectation by issuing this circular is to bring benefits to the wider community. However, the circular is not matched by preparedness and careful planning, so that its implementation in the community becomes problematic, especially for those who are directly affected by the ban, which in the end must make plans to be postponed until unpredicted time or even amended according to the situation.

Moreover, not all people in Indonesia, including the city of Manado are highly educated. Therefore any rule is often difficult to accept if it conflicts with their needs, as indicated by the data from the Central Statistics Agency of North Sulawesi Province; it shows that the human development index in the city of Manado was at 79.12 percent.[18] Apart from that, the trend of unregistered marriage contract due to accident (unwed pregnancy) in the city of Manado continues to rise,[19] even it becomes a public secret that the effect of the rapid westernization leads to promiscuity.[20]

This has led to the increase of unregistered marriages in the pandemic period after the postponement of the marriage ceremony was implemented by the KUA. If this delay continues until unpredicted time limit, then the incidence of unregistered marriage will increase. Therefore, a win-win regulation is needed for the community to suppress unregistered marriage during the pandemic, at least by opening marriage registration opportunities through digital technology so that all involving parties related to the marriage procession are visible to make agreement.

When the process of this research took place, an amendment of the circular dated twenty-three April released which had the same substance as the previous circular; letting the marriage procession as long as it was registered before the date of circular issuance, otherwise halting afterwards it. Such rules in the social and legal context are very problematic, because it may provoke unregistered marriage contracts. As addition, there are also quite risky problems, the emergence of various individual interpretation "ijtihad" from the KUA to deal with various problems in

the field that are hindered by the circulation, as the data which has been presented before.

Referring to the content of Article 1 of the Regulation of the Minister of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia Number 34 Year 2016 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the District Religious Affairs Office, the KUA has position, duty and function as a technical implementer unit at the Ministry of Religion, under and reporting to the Director General Islamic Community Guidance and operationally fostered by the Head of the Office of the Ministry of Religion in the Regency / City.

Knowing such duties and functions, it can be understood that KUA only accommodates administrative and bureaucratic works in the field, especially in carrying out services and guidance of the Islamic community in their respective working areas (Article 2). Thus, the KUA is not permitted to have individual interpretation "ijtihad" in cases that are not listed in the rules, especially allowing unregistered marriage to be held, either by the authorities themselves or by giving instructions to other authorities.

"Ijtihad" is certainly not permitted by the KUA at the administrative and bureaucratic level, especially in terms of denying the registration of marriage, because it is not in line with the rules of marriage in Indonesia which obliges registration process, such as Acts No. 1 of 1974, PP No. 9 of 1975, as well as the Compilation of Islamic Law. Thus, the legal system in Indonesia does not recognize the term unregistered marriage or such case, and does not accommodate it by being regulated in any decree. However, the dichotomy between Islamic law and national law, which has faded for years, is now re-blooming after the issuance of the marriage postponement circular despite for beneficial reasons.

KUA is the only institution that has full authority from the government to register marriages among Muslims, and there is no other institution that includes religious leaders who are considered to have the competence to marry someone. Hence, the existence of KUA in addition to fulfilling bureaucratic demands is also substantially responsible for implementing the validity of a marriage, but does not carry out "ijtihad" by the law itself. For this reason, cases that occur after a circulated marriage postponement, should receive special and serious treatment from the KUA. Because KUA in the context of marital law is obliged to provide guidance and counseling to the community to form a happy and eternal family upon regulations.

KUA as an official institution established by the State based on the law has an important role in suppressing the number of unregistered marriages such as marriages under its respective jurisdiction. This is a form of commitment of state servants in maintain the mandate of the law. When unregistered marriages are accommodated or justified by opening opportunities for unregistered marriages, it will lead to new legal problems and harm the legal order that has been on the tract so far.

The problem that may occur is the increasing number of *istbat* (ratification) of marriage when all the perpetrators of unregistered marriage make a request in the Religious Court. Although if it is not, then it is possible for a misuse of the law carried out by the authorities, the KUA officials are possible to legalize the registration of marriage after the issuance of a new circular by intentionally setting the date of marriage preceding the promulgation of the circulation, or by reason of marriage renewal (*tajdid an-nikah*), even though the product *fiqh* in Marriage Law Number 1 of 1974 Article 26 only applies on cancelation of marriage because the marriage being held in the presence of an illegal or unauthorized marriage registrar, illegitimate trustees or marriage without the presence of two witnesses and receives

the request for a marriage cancellation from a family on behalf of the husband or wife, prosecutor and husband or wife.

Therefore, legal behavior that exceeds its authority can be categorized as a violation, and regulation of the Minister of Religion No. 19 of 2018 concerning Marriage Registration Article 43 explains that the Head of District KUA, headman, and overseas marriage registration employees who violate the provisions referred to in Ministerial Regulation is subject to sanctions in accordance with existing statutory acts.

The importance of the law supremacy by the KUA through legalizing a marriage in the form of registration is the nature of *tautsiqi*, [21, p. 34] the aim and purpose are to minimize uncontrolled marriages held by Muslims. The institutional use is to place the KUA as the executor of the law as a sacred institution that has an urgent and strategic position in Muslim society. As addition, KUA may fortify the negative efforts of irresponsible parties.

Narration like this is certainly considered rigid because it seems to deny social existence that requires legal instruments for their wellbeing, but by quoting general legal principles namely; *lex dura sed tamen scripta*, where the law or the rule of law is felt to be harsh, decisive, and cruel to the public. Actually, that is how it is, because it is a consequence of every citizen to be able to obey the law as a whole. Therefore, Sudikno Mertokusumo [22, p. 3] states that no matter what happens, the rules must still be obeyed and applied.

Aside from the negative implications in the social and juridical realms, the negative implications also occur in the *fihiyyah* realm. Moreover, the reason for issuing the circular is to the benefit of people. It is encouraged to become a grip both for the KUA and for residents who are directly affected by the circulation of marriage delays. In fact, law in Islam was created not only for one purpose, that is benefit. The law in Islam is also to prevent harm. The principle of Islamic law is to bring benefit and prevent harm altogether (*jalb al-mashalih wa dar'u al-mafasid*). [23, p. 169], [24, p. 306], [25, p. 84]

Thus, when there is a conflict between two vices in one condition - as the case today in the Covid-19 pandemic, the vices to postpone marriage in an effort to prevent the spread of the Covid-19 outbreak and the detriment of unregistered marriage. Actually, then *fiqh* teaches to avoid more damage. Then, choosing a lighter damage to implement is prioritized. As the rules of *fiqh* explain: "If there are two contradictory vices (in one condition), then leave the greater vices between the two, by choosing lighter vices (to be applied)." [26, p. 526], [27, p. 89], [28, p. 286], [29, p. 87]

For measuring which badness is lighter to apply, it is better to use the following two rules as a measurement tool, namely *al-mashlahah al-'ammah muqaddam a'la al-mashlahah al-khashah* [30, p. 339] (general benefit must be put forward rather than special benefit), and *tasharruf al-imam 'ala ar-ri'iyah manuth bi al-mashlahah* [31, p. 88] (regulations made by the government are solely for the good of all community).

Based on the *fihiyyah* statement above, the benefit value that can be drawn from the circulation of marital delays by the government is that all Indonesian citizens, including the people of Manado City can avoid Covid-19 spread. One of the way to prevent the spread is not gathering a number of people. Moreover, the data shows the numbers of positive patients in the city of Manado continue to increase every day; confirmed thirty-six people, recovered five people, and died three people dated twenty-four April, [32] The issuance of the circular is the lightest choice to do

because the disadvantages are felt only by a handful of people. In contrast, if unregistered marriage practice is implemented, it may cause various new problems emerging along with it and this is very dangerous for the safety of the Indonesian as whole.

5. Conclusion

Based on the explanation above, a conclusion can be drawn that the result of the marriage postponement issuance by the Director General of Islamic Community Guidance of the Ministry of Religion of the Republic of Indonesia which must be applied by all KUAs in Indonesia including in the City of Manado, raises several negative implications, namely; in the social aspect indicated by occurrences of unregistered marriage whether identified by the KUA or not on behalf of needs; the juridical aspect is the emergence of various "ijtihad" that varied even beyond their authority because there was no punishment dictum for those who violate the circular. It is realized that the absence of systematic and directed monitoring and evaluation carried out by the Ministry of Religion Section Manado City as the person in charge is needed to maintain the rule. The last is the implication of fiqhiyyah, where the reason for the benefit is used simplistically. It is known that the point does not use the ushul fiqh as a measurement tool to value the big disadvantages (mudharat) so that we prefer the milder one. Meanwhile the severe disadvantage will be used as a reference only.

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